

ARRAYS AND ARRAYS INSTALLATION

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ANNOTATION .

This JAVA programming in the article in the language arrays and a lot sized the array announcement to do of arrays different properties cause passed . Other programming in their languages solution arrays with depends issues seeing developed _

Sign in .

Everyone programming languages JAVA arrays like with to work powers up . of JAVA main from the goals one is this safety . That's why for C and C++ languages encountered a lot problems in JAVA solution done _ Har one to the pointer when he is silent automatic means null in the manner is given From application before you each one applicable pointer your initialization and to him meaning give need _

in JAVA the array announcement to

```
do int ab [ ]
```

```
int [ ] al
```

This record array himself not an array to the object to be sent makes _ Attention give , an array size not shown .

Simple ones array make up

```
int [ ] al = {1,2,3,4,5};
```

Array the length determination in JAVA length for arrays for before determined style is used .

```
al length ;
```

in JAVA the index of the first element is 0. Of the array the most big massive element using length - 1 determination can _ If you objects array creating if you are , always new key the word to use need _

Objects array

. Objects array how to compose the following in the example seeing we go out public class Animal { private int number of legs ;

```
Animal ( int number of legs) {
```



```

this. number of legs = number of legs;}Animal [ ] a = new Animal [ 20 ] ;System.
out printin (a length + « animal »);
for ( int i = 0; i < a. length; i + + )
a [ ] = new Animal ( i % 2 + 1)* 2 );
}

```

Array initialization for also meanings the list apply can _ In this meanings circle to

brackets is taken

```

integer [ ] a = {
new integer (1) ;
new integer (2);
new integer (3);
};

```

A lot sized arrays

Also a lot sized arrays announcement to do can _

```

int [ ] [ ] a;
int [ ] a [ ];

```

One sized as in array a lot sized the array announcement in doing meanings suddenly initialization can _

```

int [ ] [ ] a = {{ 1,2,3},{5,6}};

```

Or cycle inside program work on time initialization can _ String.

String variables make up for the String class objects is used . String of variables meaning quote into is taken . Literal in binding the first a String object in the attempt in memory is made .

new literal String object when added again is made . To new literal data have is a String object is added .

String class constructors .

String type objects the same another objects like constructor using is made .

Constructor each one when called it is new object makes _

```

String c = new String (" abc ") ; of

```

the String class before determined one how many constructors there is .

Strings concatenation .

Add concatenation "+" . sign using perform can _ String is new in concatenation

object is made . Other get up Meaning String is unique to the object merging can

String n = "Number" + 4v ; Let

's say to you style one how many meanings to return need _ In this case arrays
style returnable parameter as apply comfortable _

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